

Nature of the Complexes of Benzoin with Group (IV) Halides

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Benzoin (LH) forms compounds of composition MX_3L with tetrachlorides and tetrabromides of tin and titanium and tetrachlorides of zirconium and silicon; compounds of composition SnI_4LH in the case of tin tetraiodide while 2,2'-dichlorobenzoin and 2,2'-dinitrobenzoin form compounds of composition MX_4LH at room temperature. On refluxing compounds of composition MX_2L_2 are obtained in the case of pure benzoin and of composition MX_3L in the case of substituted benzoin. From conductance, molecular weight determination and i.r. spectral studies, their structures have been elucidated.

IN continuation of the studies of the complexes of Lewis acids with benzoin and substituted benzoin¹⁻⁵ which are α -hydroxy ketones, we now report the investigations of the complexes of benzoin (LH) with the halides of group (IV) elements. Since α -hydroxy ketones are potential ligands for the formation of five co-ordinated complexes for the central atom, therefore the addition compounds of benzoin, 2,2'-dinitrobenzoin and 2,2'-dichlorobenzoin with the tetrahalides of tin, titanium, zirconium and silicon have been isolated. From the elemental analysis, molar conductance, molecular weight determination and i.r. spectral studies, an attempt has been made to elucidate their structures. The effect of electron withdrawing groups at the α -position in the ring on the tendency of benzoin to act as the donor molecule is also investigated.

Results and Discussion

It is quite surprising to note that the mixing of silicon tetrachloride and benzoin in benzene results in exothermic reaction with the liberation of hydrogen chloride gas. A compound of composition $SiCl_2L_2$ separates out. All attempts to prepare an addition compound without elimination reaction have failed. In the case of 2,2'-dichlorobenzoin and 2,2'-dinitrobenzoin, no reaction takes place at room temperature. However on refluxing, products of composition $SiCl_2L_2$ are obtained.

Tin tetrachloride and bromide and titanium tetrachloride form compounds of composition MX_3L with benzoin and of composition MX_4LH with substituted benzoin at room temperature but when these compounds are refluxed in benzene, compounds of composition MX_2L_2 are obtained. Tin tetraiodide with benzoin forms an adduct of composition SnI_4LH only. It does not form any adduct with substituted benzoin. It may be because of poor donor character of the substituted benzoin. Zirconium tetrachloride does not form any adduct with benzoin or substituted benzoin at room temperature but when refluxed in benzene, compounds of composition $ZrCl_3L$ separate out.

In Table 1 is given the list of compounds of benzoin and substituted benzoin with group (IV) metal halides which have been isolated in the present studies. Stoichiometric compositions of these compounds has been determined by the elemental analysis. All these compounds are hygroscopic in nature but are fairly stable in dry atmosphere. They are soluble in various aprotic solvents such as nitrobenzene and acetonitrile. Molar conductance values of the millimolar solutions in nitrobenzene suggest that all these adducts are nonionic in nature. Molecular weight determination in nitrobenzene indicates that compounds of molecular formula MX_2L_2 are monomeric in nature while the adducts of composition MX_3L are dimeric. Tin tetraiodide adduct is also monomeric. All these results are also included in Table 1.

Further information about the nature of these adducts has been obtained by scanning i.r. spectra of these complexes. Benzoin has two coordination sites namely carbonyl group ($C=O$) and hydroxyl group (OH) and may act as bidentate ligand. It is well known that as a result of coordination through the carbonyl oxygen the double bond character between the carbon and oxygen is reduced and this decrease in the bond order causes a bathochromic effect in the carbonyl stretching frequency $\nu(C=O)$ and it is shifted to a lower region. The OH stretching frequency generally observed in the range 3590-3650 cm^{-1} in alcohols and phenols⁶ having free hydroxyl group is lowered to 3360 cm^{-1} in pure benzoin due to strong intramolecular hydrogen bonding as has been proposed on the basis of its i.r. spectral studies in the overtone region. The carbonyl stretching frequency present at 1670 cm^{-1} in pure benzoin is lowered to 1600-1630 cm^{-1} in various adducts depending upon the acceptor strength of Lewis acids used. Thus lowering of the carbonyl stretching frequency suggests the coordination of the carbonyl oxygen of benzoin to the central metal atom. The intense absorption band at 3360 cm^{-1} due to OH stretch in pure benzoin is missing in these complexes which shows the absence of OH group in these complexes except in the case of the

TABLE I

Complex	Colour and melting pt. (°C)	Molar conductance in nitrobenzene $\text{ohm}^{-1}\text{cm}^2 \text{mole}^{-1}$	Molecular weight in nitrobenzene		Found (%)		Calcd. (%)	
			Found	Required	Metal	Halogen	Metal	Halogen
$\text{SnCl}_3 \cdot \text{Benz}$	White 110-2	2.81	818.32	872.81	26.48	23.97	27.20	24.41
$\text{SnBr}_3 \cdot \text{Benz}$	Light-yellow 111-2	1.01	1096.10	1139.33	15.98	40.02	16.35	42.11
$\text{SnCl}_3 \cdot \text{BenzH}$	Light-brown 95	1.37	802.37	838.92	13.77	57.98	14.16	60.56
$\text{TiCl}_3 \cdot \text{Benz}$	Yellow 109	0.98	699.98	731.21	12.36	28.74	13.10	29.15
$\text{ZrCl}_3 \cdot \text{Benz}$	White 168	0.87	397.22	408.97	20.01	25.31	22.30	26.04
$\text{SnCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{Benz}$	Light brown 56(d)	1.21	508.76	521.51	4.76	19.12	5.44	20.61
$\text{SnCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{Benz}$	Light-pink 90-2	1.23	602.72	611.99	18.75	11.01	19.41	11.61
$\text{SnBr}_2 \cdot 2\text{Benz}$	Light-yellow 122-3	1.31	639.36	700.90	12.73	21.33	13.46	22.83
$\text{TiCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{Benz}$	Yellow 115(d)	1.08	529.34	540.92	7.92	12.91	8.35	13.13
$\text{SnCl}_4 \cdot \text{DinitroBenzH}$	Light-brown 187(d)	1.82	549.32	562.73	20.03	24.04	21.09	25.20
$\text{SnBr}_4 \cdot \text{DinitroBenzH}$	Light-yellow 192(d)	1.86	712.63	740.70	15.12	42.10	16.03	43.20
$\text{SnCl}_4 \cdot \text{DichloroBenzH}$	White 169(d)	0.88	529.12	541.71	20.99	38.34	21.92	39.31
$\text{SnBr}_4 \cdot \text{DichloroBenzH}$	Dirty-white 178	0.78	702.13	719.72	12.43	52.97	13.10	54.36
$\text{TiCl}_4 \cdot \text{DichloroBenzH}$	Yellow 165(d)	1.63	461.61	470.93	9.99	44.68	10.17	45.24
$\text{TiCl}_4 \cdot \text{DinitroBenzH}$	Yellow 149	1.32	480.66	491.94	8.67	27.81	9.49	28.32
$\text{SnCl}_2(\text{DinitroBenz})_2$	White 173(d)	2.42	779.94	792.73	13.93	8.08	14.79	8.84
$\text{SnCl}_2(\text{DichloroBenz})_2$	White 222(d)	1.37	739.23	749.70	15.12	27.77	15.83	28.41
$\text{SnBr}_2(\text{DinitroBenz})_2$	Light-grown 189	2.33	852.81	880.71	12.91	17.93	13.48	18.17
$\text{SnBr}_2(\text{DichloroBenz})_2$	Dirty-white 201	1.48	724.32	738.72	15.11	39.92	16.07	40.38
$\text{TiCl}_2(\text{DinitroBenz})_2$	Yellow 129(d)	1.93	713.60	720.90	6.10	9.22	6.65	9.85
$\text{TiCl}_2(\text{DichloroBenz})_2$	Yellow 178(d)	0.99	669.19	678.91	6.74	30.27	7.01	31.39
$\text{ZrCl}_3 \cdot \text{DinitroBenz}$	Light-yellow 163	1.11	487.32	498.73	17.92	20.81	18.29	21.34
$\text{ZrCl}_3 \cdot \text{DichloroBenz}$	White 221	1.46	469.68	477.72	18.48	36.53	19.09	37.16
$\text{SiCl}_3 \cdot (\text{DichloroBenz})_2$	White 183	0.92	649.66	659.11	3.71	31.42	4.26	32.32
$\text{SiCl}_2 \cdot (\text{DinitroBenz})_2$	Light brown 158	0.77	691.96	701.10	3.20	9.41	3.99	10.13

(d)—with decomposition.

adduct of tin tetraiodide which shows the presence of a sharp absorption band at 3456 cm^{-1} . The shift of this particular band on complex formation with Lewis acids to a higher region suggests that hydrogen bonded OH group has become free. The absence of OH band in most of the other compounds is supported by the fact that hydrogen chloride gas is evolved during the course of the preparation of these adducts. The attachment of alcoholic oxygen to the metal ion is supported by the fact that the C-O stretching frequency present at 1094 cm^{-1} in pure benzoin is lowered to $1076-1030 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in various complexes. In the case of these adducts, new absorption bands in the range $480-560 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ have been observed which may be assigned to $\nu(\text{M}-\text{O})$ stretching frequency. In the case of tin tetrachloride adducts it is observed that 556 and 544 cm^{-1} in benzoin complexes; at 552 and 540 cm^{-1} in 2,2'-dichlorobenzoin complexes and at 536 cm^{-1} in the case of 2,2'-dinitrobenzoin complexes. In the case of titanium tetrachloride complexes, it is observed that 526 , 518 and 512 cm^{-1} for pure benzoin, 2,2'-dichlorobenzoin and 2,2'-dinitrobenzoin respectively. All these metal-oxygen bands are found in the range as has been reported in literature. In the case of zirconium tetrachloride adduct, the metal-oxygen band is found at 506 cm^{-1} . The relative lowering of $\nu(\text{M}-\text{O})$ in this case as compared to tin and titanium may be attributed to the mass effect.

Molecular formula of some of the complexes is suggestive of the five coordination number for tin and titanium. It is therefore of interest to scan carefully the i.r. spectra of these complexes in the far i.r. region. Attention has been focussed on $\nu(\text{M}-\text{O})$ and $\nu(\text{M}-\text{X})$ stretching frequencies. In pure tin tetrachloride the $\nu(\text{Sn}-\text{Cl})$ stretching frequency is observed at 403 cm^{-1} . It is observed in the range $320-280 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ for all tin complexes reported here. The bands assigned to $\nu(\text{Sn}-\text{Cl})$ stretching frequency agree well with those reported in literature. In the complexes of the type $(\text{SnCl}_3\text{L})_2$, a new absorption band at 268 cm^{-1} is observed which may be assigned to $\text{Sn}-\text{Cl} \rightarrow \text{Sn}$ linkage suggesting that dimerisation of the complex has taken place through chloro bridging rather than the ligand bridging. Similar observations have already been made by various workers^{7,8}, where the coordination number of six for the central atom has been explained through halogen bridging. In the case of the corresponding compounds of titanium the $\nu(\text{Ti}-\text{Cl})$ bands in the 394 cm^{-1} region correspond to coordination number of six for titanium. Moreover, one band at 264 cm^{-1} for the $(\text{TiCl}_3\text{L})_2$ complex is most probably due to the presence of $\text{Ti}-\text{Cl} \rightarrow \text{Ti}$ linkage. Therefore the possible structure for these complexes where dimerisation through halogen bridging takes place may be formulated as in fig. a.

Above formulation that both the chlorines are in the trans position gets support from the fact that only one type of the metal-chlorine band (apart from bridging) is found in the spectra of these complexes. There are two types of metal-oxygen bands.

(Fig. d)

From this it may be concluded that these complexes are thus octahedrally viz., chlorine atoms. The metal-oxygen stretching frequency is at the same position as has been calculated by Pollar⁹ by the force constant of the Sn-O bond from Gordy's rule which is also in good agreement with those reported by Rochow¹⁰ *et. al.* Wilkins and Haendler¹¹ have recently assigned a strong band in the region 355-398 cm^{-1} to the Sn-O stretching frequency in their tin tetrahalide complexes with pyridine N-oxide but we are unable to find the same band in our present studies. Since there has been no splitting of the bands, therefore trans positions for the chlorines may be assigned which supports the above formulation. In the case of the adducts MCl_2L_2 , from the cryoscopic studies it has been shown that unlike earlier adducts, adducts of this type are monomeric in nature. Apart from the Sn-Cl stretching frequency, assigned to trans structure (Fig. b) no absorption bands assigned to bridging chlorine are observed here. All absorption bands discussed earlier are also observed in these complexes. The possible structure where the metal may have a coordination number of six and the chlorines may have a trans disposition may be formulated as Fig. b.

(Fig. b)

Our spectra of tin tetrabromide complexes with benzoin and substituted benzoin show all negative shifts of the carbonyl stretching frequency and the shifts in O-C stretching frequency in the upper region strongly suggest the coordination of the donor molecule through oxygen and there is hardly any difference in the absorption band for tetrachloride

complexes indicating similarity of bonding in tetrachloride and tetrabromide adducts with benzoin. If the negative shift of the carbonyl frequency is a measure of the acceptor strength of Lewis acids, then tetrachlorides are better acceptors than tetrabromides and tetraiodides.

Conductance data have shown the nonionic character of these adducts though a very high polarity of the bond may be indicated. Therefore, a possible elimination reaction may be possible. T. G. A. of freshly prepared complexes has been carried out to explore the possibility of such an elimination reaction which may be helpful to understand the disposition in space of various groups. These investigations have clearly shown a definite mode of decomposition of the compounds of the type $(\text{MX}_3\text{L})_2$. By calculating the total percentage loss in weight of the complexes for different possible modes of elimination reactions in these complexes, it has been suggested by comparing these values with those of the observed percentage loss in weights from T. G. A. graphs that a molecule of benzoyl chloride, benzaldehyde and stannous chloride is formed.

Experimental

All materials employed were properly purified following the methods reported in literature.

Complexes of composition MX_3L and MX_4LH were prepared by mixing the two components (1 : 1) in dry benzene at room temperature when white crystalline compounds separated out. These complexes were filtered in dry atmosphere, washed repeatedly with boiling benzene and dried under vacuum. Complexes of composition MX_2L_2 were prepared by refluxing the components in the ratio 1 : 2 in boiling benzene for 24 hrs. On cooling complexes separated out. In the case of silicon tetrachloride, the reaction was exothermic at room temperature. The solid product was obtained after keeping the reactants over night. The stoichiometric composition of these compounds has been confirmed by the elemental analysis.

Molar conductances of the millimolar solutions of the complexes were measured in dry nitrobenzene in a cell of cell constant 0.39 cm^{-1} using Toshniwal conductivity bridge Type CLOI/OIA Sr. No. 448. Infrared spectra of the complexes were recorded on a double grating infrared spectrophotometer Perkin Elmer No. 337 and for the far i.r. spectra, Perkin Elmer No. 621. Spectra were recorded in potassium bromide beads.

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